

TABLE-1

Sl. No.	Compound	Colour	Vanadium		Nitrogen		μ_{eff} at 300°K (B. M.)
			Found %	Required %	Found %	Required %	
I	V(pic) ₃ ·2H ₂ O	Orange	11.20	11.26	9.19	9.27	2.73
II	V(dipic) ₃ ·2H ₂ O	Yellowish green	8.64	8.76	7.30	7.21	2.66
III	V ₂ (collidH) ₃ ·3H ₂ O	Orange yellow	12.96	13.02	5.42	5.36	2.60

shifted to higher frequency region upon coordination of the ring nitrogen to a metal ion^{9,10}. In the I.R. spectra of all the three complexes these bands were shifted to higher frequency region by 20-35 wave numbers and this has been considered as an evidence of coordination through the heterocyclic nitrogen. The presence of lattice water is exhibited by rather broad bands in the 3500-3200 cm⁻¹ region¹¹.

The above facts indicate that the d² V(III) entity is present in an octahedral donor environment in all the three chelates. To our knowledge these are among the few examples of V(III) chelates which are stable towards oxidation in open atmospheric conditions.

Further studies on the magnetic behaviour at low temperature structure in the solid state and reactivity of the complex species towards various oxidising agents are in progress.

References

1. R. J. H. CLARK and M. L. GREENFIELD, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1967, 409.
2. H. HARTMANN and H. L. SCHLAFFER, *Angew. Chem.*, 1954, 66, 768.
3. R. J. H. CLARK, "The Chemistry of Titanium and Vanadium", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1961.
4. B. N. FIGGS and J. LEWIS, "Progress in Inorganic Chemistry," 1964, 6, 37.
5. R. L. CARLIN and E. G. TEREZAKIS, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1967, 47, 4901.
6. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, 1968, p. 269.
7. R. J. PRUMEREDDI, A. D. LEHR and A. W. ADAMSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 249.
8. K. NAKAMOTO, Y. MORIMOTO and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 84, 2081.
9. R. J. H. CLARK and C. S. WILLIAMS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 350.
10. N. S. GILL, R. H. NUTTAL, D. E. SCAIFE and D. W. A. SHARP, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1961, 18, 79.
11. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds." Interscience Publishers, 1970, p. 166.

Study of Some Binary and Ternary Complexes of Praseodymium(III) with Substituted Salicylic Acids

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In our earlier communications^{1,2} we have described investigations on the binary and ternary complexes of Pr(III) with polyhydroxy phenolic ligands. In the present communication we are reporting for the first time the metal-ligand stability constants of ternary complexes (MAL), where M=Pr(III), A=Nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) or N-Hydroxyethylthylenediaminetriacetic acid (HEDTA) or Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) as primary ligand and L-Sulphosalicylic acid (SSA) and 3,5-Dinitrosalicylic acid (DNSA) as secondary ligand (L), by using the modified form of Irving and Rossotti titration technique.

Experimental

The details of the preparation of metal and primary ligand solutions and the instruments used are the same as described in our earlier communications^{1,2}. 0.02M solutions of SSA and DNSA were prepared by dissolving requisite quantities in doubly distilled water, and standardized potentiometrically.

The procedure employed and conditions maintained and the methods of calculations used are also the same as described earlier^{1,2}.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand Stability Constants

The formation curves drawn between $\bar{n}_A$ against pH are found to be extended between 0 to 2 for SSA and 0 to 1 for DNSA in the $\bar{n}_A$ scale indicating the early dissociation of -SO₃H group in SSA and -COOH group in DNSA. The obtained are summarised in Table 1.

Metal-ligand Stability Constants of Binary Complexes

For SSA system the formation curves are found to be extended between 0 to 3 in $\bar{n}_A$ scale indicating

the formation of three stepwise complexes between Pr(III) and SSA. In case of DNSA the precipitation was observed at pH 6.0. The calculation of $\bar{n}$ was done using data below the pH of precipitation and the formation curve were found to be extended between 0 to 1 indicating the formation 1 : 1 Pr(III) : DNSA complex. The values obtained for log K are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES $\mu = 0.2M$ AT 25°

System	Constant	Method	
		A	B
H-SSA	$\log K_1^H$	11.65	11.62
	$\log K_2^H$	2.47	2.42
H-DNSA	$\log K^H$	7.08	7.07
	$\log K_1$	6.81	6.80
Pr(III)-(SSA)	$\log K_2$	5.66	5.64
	$\log K_3$	3.63	3.61
Pr(III)-(DNSA)	$\log K$	4.94	4.93
Pr(III)-(NTA)(SSA)	$\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$	6.24	6.28
Pr(III)-(HEDTA)(SSA)	$\log K_{MAL}^{HEDTA}$	4.94	4.96
Pr(III)-(EDTA)(SSA)	$\log K_{MAL}^{EDTA}$	4.44	4.41
Pr(III)-(NTA)(DNSA)	$\log K_{MAL}^{NTA}$	3.46	3.50
Pr(III)-(HEDTA)(DNSA)	$\log K_{MAL}^{HEDTA}$	3.34	3.40
Pr(III)-(EDTA)(DNSA)	$\log K_{MAL}^{EDTA}$	3.18	3.13

Method A=Interpolation at half $\bar{n}(\bar{n}_A)$ values.
 B=Interpolation at different $\bar{n}(\bar{n}_A)$ values.

Metal-ligand Stability Constants of Mixed-ligand Complexes

The values of $\log K_{MAL}^A$ were evaluated by pointwise calculations of $\bar{n}$ and pL , where $\bar{n}$ is the average number of secondary ligands (L) attached per molecule of primary complex Pr(III)-(A). The values obtained for $\log K_{MAL}^A$ for various systems are summarised in Table 1.

The values of ternary complex formation constants for SSA are higher than DNSA. It has been observed that in cases where A=NTA, HEDTA, $\log K_{MAL}^A$ is significantly lower than $\log K_{ML_1}$. This is in good agreement with the results reported earlier^{1,2} by us with different secondary ligands. This can be explained on the basis that in case of binary complex formation ligand (L) has to approach a positively charged Pr(III) ion and more coordination positions are available for its attachment which results in $K_{ML_1} > K_{MAL}^A$. NTA acts as tetra, HEDTA as penta and EDTA as hexa dentate

ligand with Pr(III) ion, so lesser number of coordination positions are available for secondary ligand (L) in case of EDTA than with HEDTA, than with NTA system, which results in lowering of stabilities of respective ternary chelates. In case of NTA and HEDTA systems in the secondary ligand (L) has to approach the neutral species Pr(III)-(A). Whereas in case of EDTA system it has to approach a negatively charged Pr(III)-(A) species. This electrostatic effect (repulsion) also results in lowering the values of K_{MAL}^A in case of EDTA.

References

1. T. H. MHASKER and K. N. MUNSHI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14A, 421.
2. T. H. MHASKER and K. N. MUNSHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 11.

Preparation and Characterisation of 12-Heteropoly Tantalatomolybdate(VI)

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EXTENSIVE X-ray studies of the aqueous solution of potassium hexatantalate¹⁻³ showed the existence of polynuclear oxoanions $[HTa_6O_{19}]^{7-}$ and $[Ta_6O_{19}]^{8-}$. Hence it is likely that the heteropolytantalate can be prepared. Dale et al⁴ have reported sodium 12-niobotantalatomanganate(IV) and have not found the works of Lapitsku and his coworkers⁵ to be reproducible in this connection. In the present communication attempts have been made to establish some suitable conditions of formation, preparation and characterisation of a new heteropoly salt of tantalum with molybdenum as the heteroatom.

Experimental

Solutions of arbitrary concentrations of the reactants may cause immediate precipitation, when they are mixed together, leading to the formation of a compound with indefinite composition. So M/20 molybdic acid and freshly prepared⁶ M/50 potassium hexatantalate solutions were found to be workable. The variation of pH changes were recorded against volume⁷ when M/20 molybdic acid solution was gradually added into 30 ml of M/50 potassium hexatantalate solution. To corroborate the observation thermometric titrimetric method⁷ was also applied. The nature of the graphs are same as reported⁷ for 6-heteropoly tantalatomungstate. The pH at which the compound formation is expected in solution phase is around 6.2, when 30 ml of M/50 potassium hexaniobate solution is mixed with 60 ml, of M/20 molybdic acid. So for the isolation of the compound in solid state, 30 ml of potassium hexaniobate was mixed with 60 ml, solution of M/20 molybdic acid and refluxed